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Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement in Literacy Skills Development among Primary School Pupils in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design where one research question and three hypotheses were raised. The population of the study consists of all primary school teachers in Osun State, where 500 teachers were randomly selected across all schools. A researcher self-constructed questionnaire titled “Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement in Literacy Skills Development Questionnaire” (PTPILSDQ) was used. The instrument was validated by two experts in Primary Education and Educational Psychology, University of Ilorin respectively, while Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate used yielded an index of 0.85 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question, while t-test and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses formulated. The findings revealed positive perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. Also, there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers based on gender and school ownership, whereas, their perception was influenced by their years of experience. It was recommended that school authority should ensure parents are involved in activities that will enhance literacy skills development among children, there should not be gender bias in the parental involvement in activities that foster children literacy skills development, school management should ensure parents are involvement in children’s learning so as to make provisions for all necessary materials needed.

Keynotes: Parental Involvement, Impact, Literacy Skills, Development

Introduction

Learning process is a life long journey. From the moment a person is born until the golden years, people are continually learning. Parent involvement with a child’s academic studies will result in a more successful schooling experience for the child. Parents provide a multidimensional role and are considered to be their child’s first teachers and socializing agents (Weigel, et al., 2016). They are caregivers that provide a nurturing environment where a child can feel safe, while providing the essential needs that motivate active learning within the child. Therefore, parental involvement is vital in supporting a child’s literacy development (Aronson, 2016).

Parental involvement in education has a profound effect on a child’s ability to become a successful adult (Aronson, 2016). According to the No Child Left Behind Act, parental involvement is defined as the participation of parents in regular, two-way, and meaningful communication involving student academic learning and other school activities including: assisting their child’s learning, being actively involved in their child’s education at school, and serving as full partners in their child’s education and being included, as appropriate in decision making to assist in the education of their child. As a result, for parent involvement to be meaningful, parents must be willing to embrace a two-way communication between their home and school.

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Literacy can be viewed as the ability to read and write as well as listening and speaking but can be redefined and looked at from different perspectives. One definition of literacy can be defined as a control of secondary uses of language (Gee, 2011). He further looked at literacy as a discourse, or a socially accepted association among ways of using language, of thinking, and of acting that can be used to identify oneself as a member of a socially meaningful group or social network. He argued that literacy is considered to be a secondary discourse because it is both acquired and learned after primary discourses which are acquired within the family and community. In contrast to Gee (2011), Delpit (2011) defined literacy as the ability for anyone to acquire a dominant discourse and the set values that may not be the one they were born into. He further opined that anyone can acquire a dominant discourse, regardless of the environment they were born into.

The importance of literacy development is directly related to a child's success into adulthood as the soil in which the roots of literacy grows has significant impact on each child's development" (Goodman, 2010). Parental involvement greatly impacts a child's learning and literacy experiences. Parent involvement not only effects students' achievement in a positive way but it also leads to better performance as the child progresses into the higher education settings (Aronson, 2016). Compton-Lily (2019) in her opinion stated that many forms of family and community involvement influence student achievement at all ages. Students have a more positive attitude towards school and learning when parents become more involved in their child's education. As children grow out of the elementary years and begin a new stage at the middle school, parental involvement is still critical in a student's success. Parents who seek assistance from teachers help ensure their child is performing at or above grade level. Involved parents are able to offer additional resources to assist in their child's learning. Parents that provide their child with various literacy events can further enhance authentic learning experiences (Ingram, et al., 2017).

A child's academic success in reading and other content areas, is the responsibility of educators, parents, and the community (Plourde, 2015). Some parents and/or families believe that schools are supposed to teach everything to their child and they should have to do nothing. This is not true. Educating a child is the responsibility of everyone in that child's life (Gilliam, et al., 2014). The most influential people in a child's life are his/her parents (Anderson, 2010). Many parents are highly motivated to help their children, but they are uncertain about what they can do or should do to promote reading (Neuman, 2016). Although highly motivated, some families have another burden to overcome. A resource that educators can give families is information. A parent pamphlet about reading is one resource for parents to have at home. It's quick, easy to understand, and small enough to store anywhere. This pamphlet will also make a positive connection between home and school, the teacher and parents (Lin, 2013). It is a resource that gives enough information for parents to be successful in reading with their child at home, and yet not too much to be overwhelming. Being able to access and utilize this information, parents will gain a sense of contribution to their child's academic achievement (Gilliam, et al., 2014; Neuman, 2016).

Parents are the predominant influence in a child's life (Anderson, 2010). Therefore, it is important for parents to be active in their child's learning. Not only will it benefit their child, but they will also feel a sense of self-worth. By providing a how-to-reading pamphlet for parents, it is more likely that they will use it. Giving them a resource to have in hand that is easy to read and use, strengthens the possibility of parent participation. Letting parents know that there are simple things they can do to be actively involved is reassuring and satisfying for parents to perceive. Christian, et al., (2018) propounded that:

"the strong association between family literacy environment and early academic abilities suggests that relatively simple behaviors such as monitoring television viewing or taking a child to the library can substantially influence growth in academic skills, regardless of parents' educational or financial circumstances."

Compton-Lily (2019) reported that more parent involvement is needed where plans to increase parental involvement in traditional events are missing the critical connection among educators, families, and students. In order to close the gap, it was deemed evident that parent involvement had to relate to their child's academic learning in one form or another (Compton-Lily, 2019). Goodman (2010) stated that children develop notions about literacy in the same way they develop other significant learning. Theories have been developed that interpret the parent role as including involvement when the parent believes they have the ability, skills and knowledge to influence their children (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 2015).

Considering the foregoing, the vital aim of any primary education system is to provide children with opportunities to acquire numeracy, literacy and other skills that they need for their further education career. Tremendous changes have taken place in the provision of primary education. Chahe and Mwaikokesya (2018) asserted that in spite of various efforts which aimed at boosting literacy skills for children, little seems to have been done in harnessing the potential of parents and supporting families in literacy development of children. Parents value education highly, though their involvement is mostly confined to financial support (Tornblad & Widell, 2014). The identification of this actual problem regarding literacy development among school age children in Osun Central Senatorial District, Osun State motivates this study. More specific, we were interested in whether and how parents can be more involved in education so as to boost up pupils' literacy development.

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Statement of the Research Problem

The development of literacy skills among primary school pupils is a critical foundation for lifelong learning and academic success. Literacy encompasses the ability to read and write and the capacity to comprehend, analyze, and communicate effectively. In the context of Osun State, Nigeria, the educational system faces challenges in achieving optimal literacy outcomes due to various socio-economic, cultural, and systemic factors. Parental involvement is a significant determinant of pupils' literacy development, which has been extensively documented as a cornerstone for enhancing children's academic achievements (Epstein, 2011). However, the extent to which teachers perceive and value parental involvement in literacy instruction remains underexplored, particularly in developing regions like Osun State.

The gap in perception between teachers and parents about their respective roles in fostering literacy may contribute to suboptimal outcomes for pupils. Teachers in Osun State may face challenges in integrating parents into the literacy development process, either due to a lack of structured school policies or insufficient training in collaborative approaches (Ajayi, 2021). Furthermore, cultural expectations and socio-economic realities often shape how parents prioritize their involvement, potentially leading to misunderstandings or underutilization of parental resources in literacy programs (Adeyemi et al., 2018). Understanding teachers' perceptions of parental involvement is vital to addressing these challenges. Such insights can guide the design of targeted interventions that bridge the gap between school and home environments, ensuring a more holistic approach to literacy development. Without a clear understanding of these perceptions, educational policies and programs may fail to leverage the full potential of parental contributions, thereby perpetuating literacy deficits among primary school pupils in the region (UNESCO, 2022). This study seeks to explore the perceptions of teachers in Osun State regarding parental involvement in literacy skills development.

Purpose of Study

The major purpose of this research work is to examine the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. This study thus seeks to:

1. Examine the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria.
2. Determine whether there is gender difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria.
3. Find out whether there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.
4. Ascertain whether if there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the study.

1. What is the mean response score of teachers' perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on gender.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Methodology

The study focused on the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria. It employed a descriptive survey research design where the opinions of the participants were sought for the research. This research design was selected because this study intends to check whether the perception have by the teachers towards the impact of parental involvement on pupils' literacy development in Osun state is either positive or negative. According to National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (www.osunstate.gov.ng/mtss-2020-2022/), there exist 1,937 primary schools in Osun Central Senatorial District, Osun State with a total of 35,117 teachers. There are 3 Senatorial Districts

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in Osun State with 10 LGAs in each zone. The study focused on the teachers across all the primary schools as the study population. A sample of 500 teachers were sampled across the 2 Senatorial Districts, where 170 teachers from West, 160 teachers from East, and 170 teachers from Central were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Thus, a total sample of 500 teachers from both private and public primary schools were selected as the participants for the study.

The instrument adopted for this research work was a self-designed questionnaire titled “Perception of Teachers on Parental Involvement on Pupils’ Literacy Skills Development Questionnaire” (PTPIPLSDQ). The questionnaire was close ended comprising of Section A, and B. The section A comprises of demographic information of the respondents which are gender, school type, and years of experience; while section B comprised 15 items on teachers’ perception. A four likert scale was used as the response format for the instrument which are SA-Strongly Agree (4 points), A-Agree (3 points), D-Disagree (2 points), and SD-Strongly Disagree (1 point). The research instrument was validated by the experts in the field of Primary Education and Educational Psychology, while instrument reliability was established using Cronbachs’ Alpha reliability estimate which yielded a value of 0.84. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research question raised, while t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypothesis formulated.

Presentation of Results

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23.0). The result of the findings is shown below: One research question was generated and answered with the use of mean and standard deviation.

Research Question 1: *What is the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, Nigeria?*

In order to ascertain the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State, mean of responses of the teachers to each items on the questionnaire were computed, having four likert scale format of Strongly Agreed (4 points), Agreed (3 points), Disagreed (2 points), and Strongly Disagreed (1 point). In other to get the cut-off mark, the average of the total point was calculated to be 2.5 (That is; $4+3+2+1 = 10$; $10/4 = 2.5$). Therefore, any mean point below 2.5 was tagged negative while mean score above 2.5 is tagged positive. The result is presented in the table below:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation showing Teachers’ Perception

S/N	ITEMS	X̄	Rank	Remarks
1.	Parental involvement can positively influence pupils’ reading habits	2.77	1 st	Positive
2.	Teachers’ collaboration with parents to implement literacy strategies at home improves pupils’ literacy development	2.67	3 rd	Positive
3.	Parents always provide feedback on their child’s literacy development at home	2.59	8 th	Positive
4.	Parent-teacher conferences will positively contribute to pupils’ literacy development	2.62	7 th	Positive
5.	Provision of reading materials at home by the parents improves pupils’ literacy skills	2.63	5 th	Positive
6	Parents have to be supportive when it comes to literacy-related homework assignments	2.76	2 nd	Positive
7	Parental involvement influences pupils’ motivation to engage in literacy activities	2.65	4 th	Positive
8	Most of the parents always attend literacy-related events or workshops organized by the school	2.53	14 th	Positive
9	Most of the parents participate in book clubs or reading groups that involve their child	2.54	13 th	Positive
10	Collaboration with parents to create individualized literacy plans increases their involvement in child’s literacy development skills	2.57	10 th	Positive
11	Necessary materials needed to promote literacy skills development in child are provided by the parents	2.63	5 th	Positive
12	Parents always assist their children in assignment related to literacy skills development	2.58	9 th	Positive

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13	Parents are aware of the specific literacy goals set for their child in class and they are always supportive	2.41	15 th	Negative
14	Parents always assist their children with literacy-related homework	2.57	10 th	Positive
15	Parents encourage and support their child's interest in reading to improve their literacy skills development	2.56	12 th	Positive
Weighted Mean		2.61		

Table 1 above revealed the perception on parental involvement on pupils' literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State. The evidence on the teachers' perception was seen from the table above from the mean value of all the items which are all greater than 2.5 except the mean value on the item 13 which is less than 2.5. The overall mean value of **2.61** which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50 indicated that primary school teachers in Osun State have positive perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils.

Testing the Hypotheses

Three research hypotheses were formulated, and were tested with the use of t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a significant level of 0.05.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on gender.

Table 2: Summary of t-test showing the significant difference in the perception of teachers based on gender.

Gender	N	X	SD	df	t. value	Sig.	Decision
Male	211	34.87	4.12	498	0.84	0.37	Not Significant
Female	289	34.32	4.71				

From table 2 above, result shows t value = 0.84, degree of freedom (498). The null hypothesis is accepted since the significant value of 0.37 is greater than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' gender does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the male teachers is not different from what was perceived by their female counterpart. Therefore, the hypothesis above which stated there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on gender is hereby retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership.

Table 3: Summary of t-test showing the significant difference in the perception of teachers based on school ownership.

School Ownership	N	X	SD	df	t. value	Sig.	Decision
Public	239	34.87	4.12	498	0.53	0.41	Not Significant
Private	261	35.58	4.23				

From table 3 above, result shows t value = 0.53, degree of freedom (498). The null hypothesis is accepted since the significant value of 0.41 is greater than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' school ownership does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers from private schools is not different from what was perceived by their counterpart from public schools. Therefore, the hypothesis above which stated there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on school ownership is retained.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State based on years of experience.

Table 4: Summary of ONE-WAY ANOVA showing the significant difference on the perception of teachers based on years of experience.

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	61.86	3	37.93			

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Within Groups	873.91	496	23.62	.93	.04	Significant
Total	935.77	499				

From table 4 above, result showed f value = .93, degree of freedom (499). The null hypothesis is rejected since the significant value of 0.04 is less than 0.05 of Alpha level. This means that, teachers' years of experience influences their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. That is, what was perceived by the teachers was differ or influenced by their years of experience. Therefore, the null hypothesis above which stated that there is no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on years of experience is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils based on years of experience.

Discussion of the Findings

The study above revealed that there was positive perception teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State. This was revealed by the overall mean value 2.61 of the total response from the respondents which is greater than the cut-off point of 2.5. This showed that primary school teachers in Osun State have positive perception that parental involvement has impact on literacy skills development among pupils. This is as a result of the significance parental involvement plays in hastening the literacy skills development in child. This corroborates the assertion of Anderson (2010), who affirmed that parents are the predominant influence in a child's life, and it is important for parents to be active in their child's learning. Not only will it benefit their child, but they will also feel a sense of self-worth. By providing a how-to-reading pamphlet for parents, it is more likely that they will use it. Giving them a resource to have in hand that is easy to read and use, strengthens the possibility of parent participation. Letting parents know that there are simple things they can do to be actively involved is reassuring and satisfying for parents to perceive.

Furthermore, it was revealed from the findings that there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of gender. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.37 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' gender does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the male teachers is not different from was what perceived by their female counterpart. This goes in line with the submission of Plourde, (2015) who submitted that a child's academic success in reading and other content areas, is the responsibility of educators, parents, and the community irrespective of their gender. Some parents and/or families believe that schools are supposed to teach everything to their child and they should have to do nothing.

More so, the findings showed that there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of school ownership. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.41 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' school type does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers from private schools is not different from was what perceived by their counterpart from public schools. This goes in line with the submission of Neuman, (2016) who submitted that the most influential people in a child's life are his/her parents. Many parents are highly motivated to help their children, but they are uncertain about what they can do or should do to promote reading. Although highly motivated, some families have another burden to overcome.

Also, the findings revealed there was significant difference in the perception of teachers on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils on the basis of year of experience. This was revealed by the significant value of the response 0.04 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This shows that teachers' years of experience does influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. This implies that, what was perceived by the teachers with less years of experience is different from was what perceived by their counterpart with high years of experience. This can therefore be concluded that teachers' perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State is influenced by their years of experience.

Conclusion

From the forgoing, it was concluded that teachers in primary schools in Osun State had positive perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils. Also, it was gathered from the findings that teachers' gender and the school ownership does not influence their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development

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among the pupils, whereas, teachers' years of experience does affect their perception on parental involvement in literacy skills development among primary school pupils in Osun State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffer so as to establish the impact of parental involvement on pupils' literacy skills development;

1. School authority should ensure parents are involved in activities that will enhance literacy skills development among children.
2. There should not be gender bias in the parental involvement in school activities to ensure collaborations between school and the parents to assist children in their literacy skills development.
3. School management should ensure parents are involvement in children's learning so as to make provisions for all necessary materials needed.
4. Parents' family background should not be determination for their involvement in school activities that foster speedy development of child's literacy skills.

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